

Attacking the DLMS/COSEM Advanced Metering Infrastructure

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Abstract—The Device Language Message Specification / Companion Specification for Energy Metering (DLMS/COSEM) constitutes the de-facto communications backbone of contemporary Advanced Metering Infrastructure. As deployment density grows, so too does the protocol's exposed attack surface, warranting systematic scrutiny. This paper contributes a structured catalogue of DLMS/COSEM-specific cyber-attacks. After presenting the protocol stack and the AMI architecture, we develop a threat model spanning edge meters, field-area networks, and utility head-ends. We then describe 6 attacks, grouped into three attack classes: (i) False-Data Injection, (ii) Connection Disruption and Session Hijacking, (iii) Denial-of-Service at the application and network layers. The paper concludes by outlining research directions for detecting and mitigating these threats.

Index Terms—Advanced Metering Infrastructure, Cybersecurity, DLMS, COSEM.

I. INTRODUCTION

Smart grids represent a significant evolution in electrical power systems, integrating advanced communication and control technologies to enhance efficiency, reliability, and security. Traditional power grids were designed for one-way electricity flow from centralized generation sources to consumers. In contrast, smart grids enable two-way communication, allowing for real-time monitoring, dynamic pricing, and integration of distributed generation sources such as solar and wind power. This transformation improves energy management and facilitates greater consumer participation in the energy market [1].

However, the increased complexity and interconnectedness of smart grids also introduce new cybersecurity challenges. The integration of Information Technology (IT) systems with traditional electrical infrastructure creates vulnerabilities that can be exploited through cyberattacks [2]. Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI), a key component of smart grids, is

particularly vulnerable [3]. AMI systems involve a network of smart meters, communication networks, and data management systems that collect and transmit data about energy consumption. Attacks on AMI can disrupt service distribution, compromise consumer privacy, and even lead to broader grid instability [3]. In 2018, U.S. utilities reported cyber incidents on AMI systems, including phishing, MitM attacks, and unauthorized head-end access [4]. In India, Chinese-linked actors used RATs to target load dispatch centers [5], while in Ukraine, the Sandworm group disabled grid functions via compromised metering and SCADA systems [6] [7]. Spanish researchers exposed firmware flaws in meters enabling data spoofing [8], and finally, studies showed DLMS/COSEM traffic patterns could reveal private behavior despite encryption [9]. Securing AMI systems requires addressing vulnerabilities in end systems, communication networks, and data management practices [10].

Our research focuses on the security of the Device Language Message Specification (DLMS) / Companion Specification for Energy Metering (COSEM) protocol, a widely used standard for communication in smart metering systems. DLMS/COSEM defines the structure and content of messages exchanged between meters and utility systems, facilitating applications such as remote meter reading and control [11]. While DLMS/COSEM incorporates security mechanisms, vulnerabilities have been identified that could allow attackers to bypass these protections [12]. The goal of this work is to present and highlight a set of attacks that can compromise the integrity of AMI system and cause grid instabilities and financial losses affecting the lives of thousands.

II. RELATED WORK

This section provides an overview of prior research on DLMS/COSEM security, known vulnerabilities, and relevant attacks targeting the AMI.

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DLMS/COSEM, while a widely adopted standard, faces various cyber threats. Vulnerabilities, including weak authentication mechanisms and insufficient encryption, have been identified [12]. These weaknesses can be exploited to gain unauthorized access, disrupt operations, and manipulate meter readings, leading to financial losses and grid instability. The security header is sent in plaintext even in protected Application Protocol Data Units (APDU), making it prone to modification [13]. Altering a single bit in the security header can downgrade the protection by transforming an authenticated and encrypted APDU into an encrypted-only APDU [14]. Weith [15] highlights that the presence of an authentication tag is indicated in plain text, and message authentication is optional, making it difficult to ascertain whether a partner intended authentication or not.

The threat model in smart grids encompasses various potential adversaries and attack surfaces. Threat actors range from script kiddies (i.e., unskilled individuals that use malicious scripts or programs generated by others or by generative Artificial Intelligence (AI)) to disgruntled insiders and advanced persistent threats. Attack surfaces include network-level vulnerabilities, device-level vulnerabilities (e.g., firmware exploits), and data-level vulnerabilities (e.g., data spoofing) [16]. Assumptions about the threat model often include the possibility of Man-in-the-Middle (MiTM) attacks and weak authentication levels [12]. Addressing these threats requires proactive security measures and continuous research to identify and mitigate emerging risks.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

This section describes the system model used in this research, encompassing the DLMS/COSEM protocol, the overall AMI architecture, and the threat model considered.

A. DLMS/COSEM Overview

DLMS/COSEM exposes metering equipment as a COSEM server that hosts Object Identification System (OBIS)-addressed interface objects [11]. The AMI head-end issues GET/SET/ACTION requests; unsolicited pushes allow the meter to stream events such as grid-fault alarms or load-profile bursts [16]. As shown in Fig. 1 the stack collapses the Open Systems Interconnection (OSI) model into five layers—Association Control Service Element (ACSE) and extended DLMS (xDLMS) at the application layer, the COSEM presentation layer with Adaptive External Data Representation (A-XDR) [11] or Abstract Syntax Notation One (ASN.1) encoding, a DLMS session/transport core, and High-Level Data Link Control (HDLC) or an Internet Protocol (IP) “wrapper” beneath [11]. Most field deployments favor the IP profile over Transport Control Protocol (TCP) port 4059 to benefit from acknowledgments and persistent sessions, although User Datagram Protocol (UDP) and the three-layer HDLC profile remain fully specified. To maintain session health and promptly surface link failures, DLMS/COSEM relies on profile specific timer driven keep alive exchanges, depending on the underlying data-link layer protocol:

DLMS/COSEM & OSI Layer Mapping

Fig. 1. DLMS/COSEM and OSI Mapping

- **HDLC profile (IEC 62056 46):** Each station arms an idle timer T_3 (typically 60–180s). When it expires without I (Information frames-carry user data and include embedded flow/error control), S (Supervisory frames-manage flow/error control when no data is being sent, using specific control codes) or U (Unnumbered frames-handle link and session management tasks and can carry control or system-level data) frames, the meter or head-end sends a supervisory Receive Ready (RR) frame with the P flag set to 1; the peer must answer with RR activating the F flag. Missing the reply closes the logical link, so the stack restarts with Set Normal Response Mode (SNRM) or Application Association Request (AARQ) [17].
- **IP wrapper profile (IEC 62056 47):** The server configures an application layer association idle timer (5–15 minutes is common). When it elapses, the client transmits a tiny, fully secured APDU. Often a GET Request for the device clock or a zero length TEST APDU; the confirmed response refreshes the timer on both sides and keeps Network Address Translation (NAT) entries alive. If the poll is not acknowledged, the server releases the association and closes the socket [18], [19].

Because these keep alive messages carry normal DLMS security headers and monotonically increasing frame counters, replayed or spoofed probes are rejected. Operators can therefore detect connectivity loss - or a Denial of Service (DoS) attempt - within a single timer interval while incurring minimal bandwidth or energy overhead [20].

As shown in Fig. 2, an HDLC profile session is opened with the SNRM handshake before the application layer AARQ/AARE:

- 1) **SNRM → UA:** The primary station (hand held probe,

Fig. 2. DLMS/COSEM Connection & Communication Flow [16]

optical head, or AMI head-end) sends an unnumbered SNRM frame asking the meter to enter Normal Response Mode (NRM); the meter replies with User Association (UA). The SNRM information field negotiates payload size, receive window, HDLC address length, and the idle timer hints T_1 , T_2 , T_3 as ID-L(Length)-V(Value) triplets. If either side rejects the proposal it returns a modified UA, issues SNRM(R), or, in the worst case, a Disconnected Mode (DM).

- 2) **AARQ** → **AARE**: Once the link parameters are accepted, the client submits an Association Control Service Element (ACSE) AARQ; the meter responds with an Application Association Response (AARE), establishing the COSEM Application Association [16].
- 3) **Protected APDU flow**: All subsequent GET/SET/ACTION (or unsolicited pushes) pass through the optional security sub layer that applies Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) 128 Galois/Counter Mode (GCM) and one of three authentication grades: None, Low-Level Security (LLS) (i.e., plain-text password), or High-Level Security (HLS) (e.g. via Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA) / Elliptic-curve Diffie-Hellman (ECDH) mutual challenge) [16].
- 4) **Keep alive**: During the session, timer-driven keep alives safeguard connectivity:
 - T_3 watchdog in HDLC—lack of an RR(P)/RR(F) exchange triggers a fresh SNRM restart [17].
 - Idle poll APDU in the IP wrapper—missed confirmation causes the server to release the association and close the socket [18], [19].

Because SNRM lets the head end tune frame size and windows to PLC, RF mesh, or cellular latency, and keeps even the parameter negotiation confidential, it underpins both resource optimization and fault recovery on AMI links. Addressing then combines a one byte client ID (16 equals to public client) with a logical/physical server address split, enabling coarse roles plus fine grained object permissions in a transport agnostic, meter friendly protocol suite [11].

B. AMI Architecture

AMI is best understood as a multi-layered cyber-physical ecosystem rather than a single product deployment [21]. It provides an intelligent connection between consumers and system operators [21]. Its architecture couples edge-level metering and control devices with enterprise analytics through a tiered communications backbone, enabling bidirectional data-and-control flows between consumers and utility operations. It is a fully configured infrastructure that must be integrated into existing and new utility processes and applications [21].

The AMI architecture can be broken down into the following domains:

- **Edge (premise) domain**: At residential and commercial/industrial sites, a solid-state smart meter measures consumption, records power-quality events, and hosts local applications such as remote connect/disconnect, outage notification, and pre-payment. The smart meter is the node through which two additional subsystems attach: a) A Home/Local Area Network (HAN/LAN) that links thermostats, load-control switches, and customer-owned DER in real time, b) An in-home display or consumer portal that exposes price signals and energy-usage feedback, fostering demand-response behavior.
- **Field-area domain**: Groups of smart meters report to a communications layer comprising Radio Frequency (RF) mesh, Power Line Communication (PLC), or fiber links. Where densities are high, data are first aggregated by neighborhood data concentrators before entering the wide-area network; rural topologies may back-haul directly. Choice of medium must balance latency, bandwidth, terrain, and future grid-modernization use-cases.
- **Head-end and metering domain**: At the utility perimeter, an AMI Head-End receives field traffic, authenticates devices, and performs protocol translation. Raw interval data are validated, edited, and estimated inside a Meter Data Management System, which also time-synchronizes, stores, and exposes granular load profiles to downstream applications through secure Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). The service provider employs systems that collect and analyze AMI data to help optimize operations, billing, and consumer service [21]. AMI enables a more distributed operating model that aims to reduce the vulnerability of the grid to attacks [21].

IV. DLMS/COSEM CYBERATTACKS

This section systematically details and outlines cyberattacks targeting DLMS / COSEM-based smart metering systems.

Fig. 3. AMI Experimental Topology

These attacks were developed and tested in a experimental setup as shown in Fig. 3, covering the Energy Use Case under the PHOENIX Project. Each attack is described with clear methodology, practical insights, and precise impacts. The attacks are categorized by their functional nature, uniqueness, and severity.

A. False Data Injection Attacks

False Data Injection (FDI) attacks seek to compromise data integrity within the AMI: by injecting manipulated meter readings or forged measurement values they can distort grid state estimation, falsify billing, or trigger misguided operational decisions. Because DLMS/COSEM treats every register as an addressable OBIS object, an adversary who tampers with ReadRequest/ReadResponse frames can covertly substitute or zero out measurements. Detecting such abuse hinges on protocol aware packet inspection and anomaly detection analytics.

1) *Register Manipulation*: The adversary's primary objective is to alter individual meter readings - by inflating or deflating kWh totals or power quality metrics - so that billing or grid analytics are wrong while values still appear normal.

Attack Methodology: Initially, the attacker performs a MitM attack between the smart meter and the AMI head-end software. By passively intercepting network packets, the attacker extracts logical identifiers (hexadecimal logical names) of specific registers from intercepted DLMS ReadRequests. Having obtained the register identifiers, the attacker actively modifies subsequent ReadRequests, replacing requested register names with others (preferably registers with highly fluctuating values, like voltage). The internal scaler of these manipulated registers amplifies the distortion effect, generating significantly misleading values.

Prerequisites & Limitations: This attack requires precise knowledge of the DLMS framing structure and register mapping, while the innercepted packets require careful manipulation of payload data without violating the DLMS framing protocol, ensuring packet acceptance by the smart meter.

2) *Response Zeroing Attack*: Here the attacker aims to erase the measurement of energy consumption entirely by setting specific registers to zero, power, current, and voltage measurements appear to be zero, thus suppressing load-related alarms and charging customers.

Attack Methodology: The attacker employs MitM techniques to intercept DLMS ReadResponses from the smart meter

toward the AMI system. After intercepting these packets, the attacker modifies payload data, inserting zero-values across a large set of selected registers (such as power, current, and voltage measurements). The attacker having recalculated the IP checksum of the altered packets forwards them to the AMI headend.

Prerequisites & Limitations: For this attack is necessary to precisely identify and zero out the correct registers and although effective, the mismatch in expected data types (int32 versus actual measurement types) may aid early detection.

False Data Injection attacks can covertly corrupt smart meter readings and grid state estimates, leading operators to make misguided decisions that degrade network performance and incur hidden financial losses. Such subtle manipulations evade detection, allowing errors to accumulate until they cause significant billing discrepancies and operational inefficiencies.

B. Connection Disruption and Hijacking Attacks

Here the attacker targets the availability and authenticity of the DLMS session itself. By corrupting authentication frames or stealing credentials, they can either block legitimate operators from connecting or take over an existing association to issue unauthorized commands. The value for the intruder is two fold: denial of service for the utility and a stealthy foothold for deeper manipulation.

1) *DLMS Authentication Disruption (Wrong Password/ Invalid Frame)*: The purpose of this attack is to deny access to legitimate operators to the smart meter by manipulating the DLMS association handshake so that every login attempt is rejected immediately.

Attack Methodology: Through a MitM attack, the attacker intercepts DLMS AssociationRequest packets sent from the AMI software toward the smart meter during the initiation of a DLMS session. The attacker replaces the legitimate CallingAuthenticationValue used in authentication with either a random string (wrong password) or intentionally malformed data that breaches DLMS framing rules. The manipulated request results in immediate authentication rejection or DLMS frame validation errors at the smart meter, permanently terminating the session.

Prerequisites & Limitations: This attack requires knowledge of authentication procedures and is most effective particularly under DLMS low-level security modes. On the other hand, attackers must recalculate packet integrity parameters, including TCP/IP checksums, to avoid rejection due to packet corruption unrelated to the intended DLMS manipulation.

2) *Session Hijacking via Authentication Capture*: The attacker aims to compromise an active DLMS/COSEM session—disrupts the legitimate operator's session and re establishing the Association under stolen credentials—in order to issue privileged commands or exfiltrate metering data while remaining indistinguishable from an authorized client.

Attack Methodology: Initially, the attacker passively monitors AssociationRequest packets to obtain the plaintext CallingAuthenticationValue exchanged during legitimate DLMS connections. After acquiring the legitimate

authentication credentials, the attacker intentionally terminates the existing legitimate connection (using methods such as heartbeat packet disruption). During the legitimate operator's reconnection attempts, the attacker actively disrupts the session establishment (authentication disruption attacks). Simultaneously, using previously obtained credentials, the attacker initiates a parallel connection, gaining unauthorized access. After establishing the illegitimate session, the attacker performs unauthorized operations, such as control commands or data extraction.

Prerequisites & Limitations: This attack is a combination of passive credential interception and active session disruption, yet it requires precision to synchronize session hijacking with legitimate reconnection attempts, enhancing attack effectiveness.

Disruption or hijacking of DLMS sessions undermines confidence in the smart-meter infrastructure, locking out legitimate users and granting attackers privileged access. Thus essential monitoring and control functions can be affected and enabling unauthorized commands or data exfiltration, eroding the protocol's foundational security guarantees.

C. Denial-of-Service Attacks

DoS attacks disrupt the availability of DLMS/COSEM communication services, effectively blocking legitimate operator access and management functions.

1) *Heartbeat Disruption DoS Attack:* The attacker aims to disrupt the KeepAlive process so both client and server perceive the link as dead, forcing endless reconnect loops and depriving operators of real time control.

Attack Methodology: Attackers intercept heartbeat packets—regularly transmitted between AMI software and smart meters to maintain active session connections. Specifically, the attacker alters the initial packet in a sequence of heartbeat exchanges, corrupting critical data necessary for maintaining the connection integrity. Subsequent heartbeat exchanges fail, triggering automatic connection terminations after consecutive missed heartbeats.

Prerequisites & Limitations: Accurate understanding of DLMS heartbeat packet structures and expected payload formats is required since packet manipulation must be performed while preserving other framing elements to avoid premature detection or packet rejection.

2) *AMI Headend Imitation DoS Attack (Application-Layer DoS):* The attacker prevents legitimate clients from ever connecting, achieving an application layer denial of service.

Attack Methodology: The attacker employs a specialized script that perfectly imitates the legitimate AMI software (e.g., GuruX DLMS Director¹) communication patterns, precisely following DLMS session establishment protocols (Set Normal Response Mode (SNRM) and AARQ). After successful authentication, the attacker's script maintains the session open by periodically sending legitimate heartbeat (KeepAlive) messages. By continuously occupying the limited concurrent

session slots available in the smart meter, the attacker effectively denies legitimate AMI operators from initiating any new connections.

Prerequisites & Limitations: Here the adversary mimics legitimate protocol communication, making typical anomaly-based detection ineffective. On the other hand the attacker must have control over packet transmission timing that adheres to DLMS protocol session management rules.

Denial-of-Service techniques can compromise the communication link between meters and the AMI, forcing repeated manual resets and impeding real-time monitoring. These can attacks bring remote management to a standstill, jeopardizing grid reliability and inflating operational costs.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has explored the cyberthreat landscape facing AMI systems, focusing on the vulnerabilities inherent in DLMS/COSEM-based implementations. By presenting these attacks, we aim to highlight the potential for significant compromise of the cyber-physical domain of operations and its effects.

To mitigate these risks, a layered defense strategy is required—extending beyond generic best practices to include DLMS-specific technical controls. These include High-Level Security (HLS) authentication using elliptic-curve cryptography, real-time protocol-aware intrusion detection systems tailored to DLMS/COSEM command patterns, and secure session binding to prevent hijacking. Furthermore, frameworks for validating and auditing DLMS/COSEM implementations [22] can be employed to verify the security of the deployed systems along with the implementation of secure key management between servers and clients [23].

Future work should focus on the continued refinement and deployment of these countermeasures, as well as the development of new techniques to detect and mitigate emerging threats. More specifically, AI/ML-enabled anomaly detection algorithms can be developed, to identify subtle deviations from legitimate protocol usage patterns leveraging network traffic statistics, enabling the detection of abnormal behaviors [24]. Mitigation strategies for such attacks can be further explored including automated incident response and business continuity playbooks [25]. Finally, emerging attack vectors should be considered, such as Generative AI models that can reproduce complex attacks based on historical data [26].

By proactively addressing these challenges, the energy sector can ensure the continued security and reliability of smart grid infrastructure.

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¹<https://github.com/Gurux/GXDLMSDirector>

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